

MAGNIFICATION OF MBJ-NEUTROSOPHIC TRANSLATION ON G-ALGEBRA

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Abstract

In this article, we define the MBJ-neutrosophic magnified translation (MBJNMT) on G-algebra which is the combination of multiplication and translation and study significant results of MBJ-neutrosophic ideal and MBJ-neutrosophic subalgebra by using the notion of MBJ-neutrosophic magnified translation. We investigate the conversion of MBJ-neutrosophic ideal and MBJ-neutrosophic subalgebra with one another and use the idea of intersection and union to produce some important results of MBJ-neutrosophic magnified translation.

Keywords: G-algebra, MBJ-neutrosophic magnified translation.

1. Introduction

Zadeh [1] presented the theory of fuzzy set in 1965. Iseki and Tanaka [2] gave the idea of BCK-algebra in 1978. Iseki [3] introduced the notion of BCI-algebra in 1980 and it is obvious that BCK-algebra is a proper sub class of the class of BCI-algebra. Lee et al. [4] investigated the fuzzy translation, (normalized, maximal) fuzzy extension and fuzzy multiplication of fuzzy subalgebra in BCK/BCI-algebra. Link among fuzzy translation, fuzzy extension and fuzzy multiplication are also studied. Ansari et al. [5] introduced the idea of fuzzy translation, fuzzy extension and fuzzy multiplication of fuzzy β ideal of β -algebra and investigated important characteristic. Priya et al. [6] studied the PS-ideal and its level subsets. Bandaru et al. [7] defined the G-algebra. Lekkoksung [8] focused on fuzzy magnified translation in ternary hemirings, which is a extension of BCI / BCK/Q / KU / d-algebra. Senapati et al. [9] have done extensive research on intuitionistic fuzzy H-ideal in BCK/BCI-algebra. Jana et al. [10] interogated the intuitionistic fuzzy G-subalgebra. Senapati et al. [11] studied fuzzy translations of fuzzy H-ideals in BCK/BCI-algebra. Atanassov [12] introduced the intuitionistic fuzzy sets. Senapati [13] investigated the relationship among intuitionistic fuzzy translation, intuitionistic fuzzy extension and intuitionistic fuzzy multiplication in B-algebra. Kim et al. [14] defined the intuitionistic fuzzy structure of B-algebra. Senapati et al. [15] discussed the fuzzy dot subalgebra and fuzzy dot ideal of B-algebras. Priya et al. [16] has done research on fuzzy translation and fuzzy multiplication in PS-algebra. Chandramouleeswaran et al. [17] investigated fuzzy translation and fuzzy multiplication in BF/BG-algebra. Smarandache [18,19] extended the intuitionistic set to neutrosophic set through Several examples. Jun et al. [20] investigated the commutative falling neutrosophic ideals in BCK-algebra. C. H. Park [21] defined the neutrosophic

ideal in subtraction algebra and studied it through several properties. Khalid et al. [22] did the research on neutrosophic soft cubic subalgebra through significant characteristic like P-union, R-intersection etc. Khalid et al. [23] interestingly worked on intuitionistic fuzzy translation and multiplication through subalgebra and ideals. Khalid et al. [24] defined the T-neutrosophic cubic set and studied this set through ideals and subalgebras and investigated many results. Takallo et al. [25] defined and studied MBJ-neutrosophic structures and its applications in BCK/BCI-algebras Khalid et al. [26] interpreted the multiplication of neutrosophic cubic set and defined the γ -multiplication of neutrosophic cubic set and studied it with neutrosophic cubic M-subalgebra, neutrosophic cubic normal ideal and neutrosophic cubic closed normal ideal. He also studied γ -multiplication under homomorphism and cartesian product through significant characteristics. Khalid et al. [27] defined and studied the MBJ-neutrosophic T-ideal through union, intersection. further he utilized important characteristics to interrogate the MBJ-neutrosophic T-ideal under cartesian product.

The purpose of this article is to introduce the idea of MBJ-neutrosophic Magnified translation (**MBJNMT**) on G-algebra. In second section we cite some fundamental definitions which are used to develop the paper. In third section we discussed the MBJ-neutrosophic magnified translation (**MBJNMT**) of MBJ-neutrosophic ideal (**MBJNID**) and MBJ-neutrosophic subalgebra (**MBJNSU**).

2. Preliminaries

First we discuss some definitions which are used to present this article.

Definition 2.1 [3] An algebra $(Y, *, 0)$ of type $(2,0)$ is called a BCI-algebra if it satisfies the following conditions:

- i) $(t_1 * t_2) * (t_1 * t_3) \leq (t_3 * t_2)$,
- ii) $t_1 * (t_1 * t_2) \leq t_2$,
- iii) $t_1 \leq t_1$,
- iv) $t_1 \leq t_2$ and $t_2 \leq t_1 \Rightarrow t_1 = t_2$,
- v) $t_1 \leq 0 \Rightarrow t_1 = 0$, where $t_1 \leq t_2$ is defined by $t_1 * t_2 = 0$, for all $t_1, t_2, t_3 \in Y$.

Definition 2.2 [1] An algebra $(Y, *, 0)$ of type $(2,0)$ is called a BCK-algebra if it satisfies the following conditions:

- i) $(t_1 * t_2) * (t_1 * t_3) \leq (t_3 * t_2)$,
- ii) $t_1 * (t_1 * t_2) \leq t_2$,
- iii) $t_1 \leq t_1$,
- iv) $t_1 \leq t_2$ and $t_2 \leq t_1 \Rightarrow t_1 = t_2$,
- v) $0 \leq t_1 \Rightarrow t_1 = 0$, where $t_1 \leq t_2$ is defined by $t_1 * t_2 = 0$, for all $t_1, t_2, t_3 \in Y$.

Definition 2.3 [7] A non-empty set Y with a constant 0 and a binary operation $*$ is said to be G-algebra if it satisfies the following axioms.

$$G1: t_1 * t_1 = 0$$

$$G2: t_1 * (t_1 * t_2) = t_2, \text{ for all } t_1, t_2 \in Y$$

A G-algebra is denoted by $(Y, *, 0)$.

Definition 2.4 [7] A non-empty subset S of G -algebra Y is called a G -subalgebra of Y if $t_1 * t_2 \in S \forall t_1, t_2 \in S$.

Definition 2.5 [15] A non-empty subset I of a G -algebra Y is called an ideal if for any $t_1, t_2 \in Y$,

- (i) $0 \in I$,
- (ii) $t_1 * t_2 \in I$ and $t_2 \in I \Rightarrow t_1 \in I$.

Definition 2.5 [6] Let Y be a PS-algebra. A fuzzy set B of Y is called a fuzzy PS ideal of Y if it satisfies the following conditions:

- i) $\phi(0) \geq \phi(t_1)$,
- ii) $\phi(t_1) \geq \min\{\phi(t_2 * t_1), \phi(t_2)\}$, for all $t_1, t_2 \in Y$.

Fuzzy and Neutrosophic Logics

Let Y be a group of objects denoted generally by t_1 . Then a fuzzy set B of Y is defined as $B = \{ \langle t_1, \phi_B(t_1) \rangle \mid t_1 \in Y \}$, where $\phi_B(t_1)$ is called the membership value of t_1 in B and $\phi_B(t_1) \in [0,1]$.

A fuzzy set B [6] of PS-algebra Y is called a fuzzy PS subalgebra of Y if $\phi(t_1 * t_2) \geq \min\{\phi(t_1), \phi(t_2)\}$, for all $t_1, t_2 \in Y$.

Let a fuzzy subset B [4], [5] of Y and $\alpha \in [0,1 - \sup\{\phi_B(t_1) \mid t_1 \in Y\}]$. A mapping $(\phi_B)_\alpha^T \mid Y \rightarrow [0,1]$ is said to be a fuzzy α translation of ϕ_B if it satisfies $(\phi_B)_\alpha^T(t_1) = \phi_B(t_1) + \alpha$, for all $t_1 \in Y$.

Let a fuzzy subset B [4], [5] of Y and $\alpha \in [0,1]$. A mapping $(\phi_B)_\alpha^M \mid Y \rightarrow [0,1]$ is said to be a fuzzy α multiplication of B if it satisfies $(\phi_B)_\alpha^M(t_1) = \alpha \cdot (\phi_B(t_1))$, for all $t_1 \in Y$.

An intuitionistic fuzzy set (IFS) [12] B over Y is an object having the form $B = \{ \langle t_1, \phi_B(t_1), \psi_B(t_1) \rangle \mid t_1 \in Y \}$, where $\phi_B(t_1) \mid Y \rightarrow [0,1]$ and $\psi_B(t_1) \mid Y \rightarrow [0,1]$, with the condition $0 \leq \phi_B(t_1) + \psi_B(t_1) \leq 1$, for all $t_1 \in Y$. $\phi_B(t_1)$ and $\psi_B(t_1)$ represent the degree of existanceship and the degree of non-existanceship of the element t_1 in the set B respectively.

Let $B = \{ \langle t_1, \phi_B(t_1), \psi_B(t_1) \rangle \mid t_1 \in Y \}$ and $C = \{ \langle t_1, \phi_C(t_1), \psi_C(t_1) \rangle \mid t_1 \in Y \}$ be two IFSs [12] on Y . Then intersection and union of A and B are indicated by $A \cap B$ and $A \cup B$ respectively and are given by

$$A \cap B = \{ \langle t_1, \min(\phi_A(t_1), \phi_B(t_1)), \max(\psi_A(t_1), \psi_B(t_1)) \rangle \mid t_1 \in Y \},$$

$$A \cup B = \{ \langle t_1, \max(\phi_A(t_1), \phi_B(t_1)), \min(\psi_A(t_1), \psi_B(t_1)) \rangle \mid t_1 \in Y \}.$$

An IFS [14] $B = \{ \langle t_1, \phi_B(t_1), \psi_B(t_1) \rangle \mid t_1 \in Y \}$ of Y is called an IFSU of Y if it satisfies these two conditions:

- (i) $\phi_B(t_1 * t_2) \geq \min\{\phi_B(t_1), \phi_B(t_2)\}$,
- (ii) $\psi_B(t_1 * t_2) \leq \max\{\psi_B(t_1), \psi_B(t_2)\}$, for all $t_1, t_2 \in Y$.

An IFS $B = \{ \langle t_1, \phi_B(t_1), \psi_B(t_1) \rangle \mid t_1 \in Y \}$ of Y is said to be an IFID of Y if it satisfies these three conditions:

- (i) $\phi_B(0) \geq \phi_B(t_1), \psi_B(0) \leq \psi_B(t_1)$,
- (ii) $\phi_B(t_1) \geq \min\{\phi_B(t_1 * t_2), \phi_B(t_2)\}$,

(iii) $\psi_B(t_1) \leq \max\{\psi_B(t_1 * t_2), \psi_B(t_2)\}$, for all $t_1, t_2 \in Y$.

Let ϕ be a fuzzy subset [8] of Y , $\alpha \in [0, T]$ and $q \in [0, 1]$. A mapping $\phi_{\beta\alpha}^{MT} | Y \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is said to be a fuzzy magnified $q\alpha$ translation of ϕ if it satisfies: $\phi_{\beta\alpha}^{MT}(t_1) = \beta \cdot \phi(t_1) + \alpha$ for all $t_1 \in Y$.

Let Y be a non empty set. MBJ-neutrosophic set [25] in Y , is a structure of the form $C = \{(M_C t_1, \widehat{B}_C t_1, J_C t_1) | t_1 \in Y\}$ where M_C and J_C are fuzzy sets in Y and M_C is a truth membership function, J_C is a false membership function and \widehat{B} is interval valued fuzzy set in Y and is an Indeterminate Interval Valued membership function.

Let $C = (M_C, \widehat{B}_C, J_C)$ is a MBJ-neutrosophic set of B-algebra Y . Let $t \in [0, 1]$, then B is called MBJ-neutrosophic T-ideal (MBJNTID) of Y if it fulfills these assertions:

- i) $M_C(0) \geq M_C(t_1), \widehat{B}_C(0) \geq \widehat{B}_C(t_1)$ and $J_C(0) \leq J_C(t_1)$.
- ii) $M_C(t_1 * t_3) \geq \min\{M_C((t_1 * t_2) * t_3), M_C(t_2)\}$.
- iii) $\widehat{B}_C(t_1 * t_3) \geq \text{rmin}\{\widehat{B}_C((t_1 * t_2) * t_3), \widehat{B}_C(t_2)\}$.
- iv) $J_C(t_1 * t_3) \leq \max\{J_C((t_1 * t_2) * t_3), J_C(t_2)\}$.

3. MBJ-neutrosophic Magnified Translation

In this section, we define MBJ-neutrosophic magnified translation **MBJNMT** and investigate some of its characteristics. we use $H = \inf\{J_C(t_1) | t_1 \in Y\}$ for any **MBJNS** $C = (M_C, \widehat{B}_C, J_C)$ of Y .

Definition 3.1 Let $C = (M_C, \widehat{B}_C, J_C)$ be a **MBJNS** of Y and $p, q, s \in [0, H]$, $\lambda \in [0, 1]$. An object having the form $C_{\lambda p, q, s}^{MT} = \{(M_C)_{\lambda p}^{MT}, (\widehat{B}_C)_{\lambda q}^{MT}, (J_C)_{\lambda s}^{MT}\}$ is said to be a **MBJNMT** of C , when $(M_C)_{\lambda p}^{MT}(t_1) = \lambda \cdot M_C(t_1) + p$, $(\widehat{B}_C)_{\lambda q}^{MT}(t_1) = \lambda \cdot \widehat{B}_C(t_1) + q$, $(J_C)_{\lambda s}^{MT}(t_1) = \lambda \cdot J_C(t_1) - s$ for all $t_1 \in Y$.

Example 3.1 Let $Y = \{0, 1, 2\}$ be a G-algebra. A MBJ-neutrosophic $C = (M_C, \widehat{B}_C, J_C)$ of Y is defined as

$$M_C(t_1) = \begin{cases} [0.2, 0.4] & \text{if } t_1 = 0 \\ [0.5, 0.7] & \text{if otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$\widehat{B}_C(t_1) = \begin{cases} [0.4, 0.6] & \text{if } t_1 = 0 \\ [0.5, 0.8] & \text{if otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$J_C(t_1) = \begin{cases} [0.3, 0.5] & \text{if } t_1 = 0 \\ [0.6, 0.8] & \text{if otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Then C is a MBJ-neutrosophic subalgebra, choose $\lambda = 0.2, p = 0.04, q = 0.05, s = 0.06$ then the mapping $C_{(0.2)(0.04, 0.05, 0.06)}^{MT} | Y \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is given by

$$(M_C)_{0.2 \ 0.04}^{MT}(t_1) = \begin{cases} [0.08, 0.12] & \text{if } t_1 = 1 \\ [0.14, 0.18] & \text{if otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$(\widehat{B}_C)_{0.2 \ 0.05}^{MT}(t_1) = \begin{cases} [0.13, 0.17] & \text{if } t_1 = 1 \\ [0.15, 0.21] & \text{if otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$(J_C)_{0.2 \ 0.06}^{MT}(t_1) = \begin{cases} [0, 0.04] & \text{if } t_1 = 1 \\ [0.06, 0.1] & \text{if otherwise} \end{cases}$$

which imply $(M_C)_{(0.2)(0.04)}^{MT}(t_1) = (0.2) \cdot M_C(t_1) + 0.04$, $(\widehat{B}_C)_{(0.2)(0.05)}^{MT}(t_1) = (0.2) \cdot B_C(t_1) + 0.05$, $(J_C)_{(0.2)(0.06)}^{MT}(t_1) = (0.2) \cdot J_C(t_1) - 0.06$ for all $t_1 \in Y$. Hence $C_{(0.2)(0.04,0.05,0.06)}^{MT}$ is a MBJ-neutrosophic magnified (0.1)(0.02,0.03,0.04) translation.

Theorem 3.1 Let C be a MBJ subset of Y such that $p, q, s \in [0, H]$, $\lambda \in [0, 1]$ and a mapping $B_{\lambda p, q, s}^{MT}|Y \rightarrow [0, 1]$ be a **MBJNMT** of C . If C is **MBJNSU** of Y , then $C_{\lambda p, q, s}^{MT}$ is a **MBJNSU** of Y .

Proof. Let C be a **MBJNS** of Y , $p, q, s \in [0, H]$, $\lambda \in [0, 1]$ and a mapping $B_{\lambda p, q, s}^{MT}|Y \rightarrow [0, 1]$ be a **MBJNMT** of C . Suppose C is a **MBJNSU** of Y . Then $M_C(t_1 * t_2) \geq \min\{M_C(t_1), M_C(t_2)\}$, $\widehat{B}_C(t_1 * t_2) \geq \text{rmin}\{\widehat{B}_C(t_1), \widehat{B}_C(t_2)\}$, $J_C(t_1 * t_2) \leq \max\{J_C(t_1), J_C(t_2)\}$. Now

$$\begin{aligned} (M_C)_{\lambda p}^{MT}(t_1 * t_2) &= \lambda \cdot M_C(t_1 * t_2) + p \\ &\geq \lambda \cdot \min\{M_C(t_1), M_C(t_2)\} + p \\ &= \min\{\lambda \cdot M_C(t_1) + p, \lambda \cdot M_C(t_2) + p\} \\ (M_C)_{\lambda p}^{MT}(t_1 * t_2) &= \min\{(M_C)_{\lambda p}^{MT}(t_1), (M_C)_{\lambda p}^{MT}(t_2)\} \\ (M_C)_{\lambda p}^{MT}(t_1 * t_2) &\geq \min\{(M_C)_{\lambda p}^{MT}(t_1), (M_C)_{\lambda p}^{MT}(t_2)\}, \\ (\widehat{B}_C)_{\lambda q}^{MT}(t_1 * t_2) &= \lambda \cdot \widehat{B}_C(t_1 * t_2) + q \\ &\geq \lambda \cdot \text{rmin}\{\widehat{B}_C(t_1), \widehat{B}_C(t_2)\} + q \\ &= \text{rmin}\{\lambda \cdot \widehat{B}_C(t_1) + q, \lambda \cdot \widehat{B}_C(t_2) + q\} \\ (\widehat{B}_C)_{\lambda q}^{MT}(t_1 * t_2) &= \text{rmin}\{(\widehat{B}_C)_{\lambda q}^{MT}(t_1), (\widehat{B}_C)_{\lambda q}^{MT}(t_2)\} \\ (\widehat{B}_C)_{\lambda q}^{MT}(t_1 * t_2) &\geq \text{rmin}\{(\widehat{B}_C)_{\lambda q}^{MT}(t_1), (\widehat{B}_C)_{\lambda q}^{MT}(t_2)\}, \\ (J_C)_{\lambda s}^{MT}(t_1 * t_2) &= \lambda \cdot J_C(t_1 * t_2) - s \\ &\leq \lambda \cdot \max\{J_C(t_1), J_C(t_2)\} - s \\ &= \max\{\lambda \cdot J_C(t_1) - s, \lambda \cdot J_C(t_2) - s\} \\ (J_C)_{\lambda s}^{MT}(t_1 * t_2) &= \max\{(J_C)_{\lambda s}^{MT}(t_1), (J_C)_{\lambda s}^{MT}(t_2)\} \\ (J_C)_{\lambda s}^{MT}(t_1 * t_2) &\geq \max\{(J_C)_{\lambda s}^{MT}(t_1), (J_C)_{\lambda s}^{MT}(t_2)\}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence **MBJNMT** $C_{\lambda p, q, s}^{MT}$ is a **MBJNSU** of Y .

Theorem 3.2 Let C be a MBJ-neutrosophic set of Y such that $p, q, s \in [0, H]$, $\lambda \in [0, 1]$ and a mapping $C_{\lambda p, q, s}^{MT}|Y \rightarrow [0, 1]$ be a **MBJNMT** of C . If $C_{\lambda p, q, s}^{MT}$ is **MBJNSU** of Y . Then C is a **MBJNSU** of Y .

Proof. Let C be a MBJ-neutrosophic subset of Y , where $p, q, s \in [0, H]$, $\lambda \in [0, 1]$ and a mapping $C_{\lambda p, q, s}^{MT}|Y \rightarrow [0, 1]$ be a **MBJNMT** of C . Let $C_{\lambda p, q, s}^{MT}$ is a **MBJNSU** of Y , then

$$\begin{aligned}
\lambda \cdot M_C(t_1 * t_2) + p &= (M_C)_{\lambda p}^{MT}(t_1 * t_2) \\
&\geq \min\{(M_C)_{\lambda p}^{MT}(t_1), (M_C)_{\lambda p}^{MT}(t_2)\} \\
&= \min\{\lambda \cdot M_C(t_1) + p, \lambda \cdot M_C(t_2) + p\} \\
\lambda \cdot M_C(t_1 * t_2) + p &= \lambda \cdot \min\{M_C(t_2), M_C(t_1)\} + p, \\
\lambda \cdot \widehat{B}_C(t_1 * t_2) + q &= (\widehat{B}_C)_{\lambda q}^{MT}(t_1 * t_2) \\
&\geq \text{rmin}\{(\widehat{B}_C)_{\lambda q}^{MT}(t_1), (\widehat{B}_C)_{\lambda q}^{MT}(t_2)\} \\
&= \text{rmin}\{\lambda \cdot \widehat{B}_C(t_1) + q, \lambda \cdot \widehat{B}_C(t_2) + q\} \\
\lambda \cdot \widehat{B}_C(t_1 * t_2) + q &= \lambda \cdot \text{rmin}\{\widehat{B}_C(t_2), \widehat{B}_C(t_1)\} + q, \\
\lambda \cdot J_C(t_1 * t_2) - s &= (J_C)_{\lambda s}^{MT}(t_1 * t_2) \\
&\leq \max\{(J_C)_{\lambda s}^{MT}(t_1), (J_C)_{\lambda s}^{MT}(t_2)\} \\
&= \max\{\lambda \cdot J_C(t_1) - s, \lambda \cdot J_C(t_2) - s\} \\
\lambda \cdot J_C(t_1 * t_2) - s &= \lambda \cdot \max\{J_C(t_2), J_C(t_1)\} - s,
\end{aligned}$$

which imply $M_C(t_1 * t_2) \geq \min\{M_C(t_1), M_C(t_2)\}$, $\widehat{B}_C(t_1 * t_2) \geq \text{rmin}\{\widehat{B}_C(t_1), \widehat{B}_C(t_2)\}$, $J_C(t_1 * t_2) \leq \max\{J_C(t_1), J_C(t_2)\}$ for all $t_1, t_2 \in Y$. Hence C is a **MBJNSU** of Y .

Theorem 3.3 If C is a **MBJNID** of Y . Then **MBJNMT** $C_{\lambda p, q, s}^{MT}$ of C is a **MBJNID** of Y for all $p, q, s \in [0, H_0]$ and $\lambda \in (0, 1]$.

Proof. Suppose $C = (M_C, \widehat{B}_C, J_C)$ is a **MBJNID** of Y . Then

$$\begin{aligned}
(M_C)_{\lambda p}^{MT}(0) &= \lambda \cdot M_C(0) + p \geq \lambda \cdot M_C(t_1) + p \\
(M_C)_{\lambda p}^{MT}(0) &= (M_C)_{\lambda p}^{MT}(t_1), \\
(\widehat{B}_C)_{\lambda q}^{MT}(0) &= \lambda \cdot \widehat{B}_C(0) + q \geq \lambda \cdot \widehat{B}_C(t_1) + q \\
(\widehat{B}_C)_{\lambda q}^{MT}(0) &= (\widehat{B}_C)_{\lambda q}^{MT}(t_1), \\
(J_C)_{\lambda s}^{MT}(0) &= \lambda \cdot J_C(0) - s \leq \lambda \cdot J_C(t_1) - s \\
(J_C)_{\lambda s}^{MT}(0) &= (J_C)_{\lambda s}^{MT}(t_1)
\end{aligned}$$

Now

$$\begin{aligned}
(M_C)_{\lambda p}^{MT}(t_1) &= \lambda \cdot M_C(t_1) + p \\
&\geq \lambda \cdot \min\{M_C(t_1 * t_2), M_C(t_2)\} + p \\
&= \min\{\lambda \cdot M_C(t_1 * t_2) + p, \lambda \cdot M_C(t_2) + p\}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
(M_C)_{\lambda_p}^{MT}(t_1) &= \min\{(M_C)_{\lambda_p}^{MT}(t_1 * t_2), (M_C)_{\lambda_p}^{MT}(t_2)\} \\
&\Rightarrow (M_C)_{\lambda_p}^{MT}(t_1) \geq \min\{(M_C)_{\lambda_p}^{MT}(t_1 * t_2), (M_C)_{\lambda_p}^{MT}(t_2)\}, \\
(\widehat{B}_C)_{\lambda_q}^{MT}(t_1) &= \lambda \cdot \widehat{B}_C(t_1) + q \\
&\geq \lambda \cdot \text{rmin}\{\widehat{B}_C(t_1 * t_2), \widehat{B}_C(t_2)\} + q \\
&= \text{rmin}\{\lambda \cdot \widehat{B}_C(t_1 * t_2) + q, \lambda \cdot \widehat{B}_C(t_2) + q\} \\
(\widehat{B}_C)_{\lambda_q}^{MT}(t_1) &= \text{rmin}\{(\widehat{B}_C)_{\lambda_q}^{MT}(t_1 * t_2), (\widehat{B}_C)_{\lambda_q}^{MT}(t_2)\} \\
&\Rightarrow (\widehat{B}_C)_{\lambda_q}^{MT}(t_1) \geq \text{rmin}\{(\widehat{B}_C)_{\lambda_q}^{MT}(t_1 * t_2), (\widehat{B}_C)_{\lambda_q}^{MT}(t_2)\}, \\
(J_C)_{\lambda_s}^{MT}(t_1) &= \lambda \cdot J_C(t_1) - s \\
&\leq \lambda \cdot \max\{J_C(t_1 * t_2), J_C(t_2)\} - s \\
&= \max\{\lambda \cdot J_C(t_1 * t_2) - s, \lambda \cdot J_C(t_2) - s\} \\
(J_C)_{\lambda_s}^{MT}(t_1) &= \max\{(J_C)_{\lambda_s}^{MT}(t_1 * t_2), (J_C)_{\lambda_s}^{MT}(t_2)\} \\
&\Rightarrow (J_C)_{\lambda_s}^{MT}(t_1) \leq \max\{(J_C)_{\lambda_s}^{MT}(t_1 * t_2), (J_C)_{\lambda_s}^{MT}(t_2)\}
\end{aligned}$$

for all $t_1, t_2 \in Y$ and all $p, q, s \in [0, H]$, $\lambda \in (0, 1]$. Hence $C_{\lambda, p, q, s}^{MT}$ of C is a **MBJNID** of Y .

Theorem 3.4 If C is a MBJ-neutrosophic set of Y such that **MBJNMT** $C_{\lambda, p, q, s}^{MT}$ of C is a **MBJNID** of Y for all $p, q, s \in [0, H]$ and $\lambda \in (0, 1]$, then C is a **MBJNID** of Y .

Proof. Suppose **MBJNMT** $C_{\lambda, p, q, s}^{MT}$ is a **MBJNID** of Y for some $p, q, s \in [0, H]$, $\lambda \in (0, 1]$ and $t_1, t_2 \in Y$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
\lambda \cdot M_C(0) + p &= (M_C)_{\lambda_p}^{MT}(0) \\
&\geq (M_C)_{\lambda_p}^{MT}(t_1) \\
\lambda \cdot M_C(0) + p &= \lambda \cdot M_C(t_1) + p, \\
\lambda \cdot \widehat{B}_C(0) + q &= (\widehat{B}_C)_{\lambda_q}^{MT}(0) \\
&\geq (\widehat{B}_C)_{\lambda_q}^{MT}(t_1) \\
\lambda \cdot \widehat{B}_C(0) + q &= \lambda \cdot \widehat{B}_C(t_1) + q, \\
\lambda \cdot J_C(0) - s &= (J_C)_{\lambda_s}^{MT}(0) \\
&\leq (J_C)_{\lambda_s}^{MT}(t_1) \\
\lambda \cdot J_C(0) - s &= \lambda \cdot J_C(t_1) - s,
\end{aligned}$$

which imply $M_C(0) \geq M_C(t_1), \widehat{B}_C(0) \geq \widehat{B}_C(t_1), J_C(0) \leq J_C(t_1)$. Now, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
& \lambda \cdot M_C(t_1) + p = (M_C)_{\lambda p}^{MT}(t_1) \\
& \geq \min\{(M_C)_{\lambda p}^{MT}(t_1 * t_2), (M_C)_{\lambda p}^{MT}(t_2)\} \\
& = \min\{\lambda \cdot M_C(t_1 * t_2) + p, \lambda \cdot M_C(t_2) + p\} \\
& \lambda \cdot M_C(t_1) + p = \lambda \cdot \min\{M_C(t_1 * t_2), M_C(t_2)\} + p, \\
& \lambda \cdot \widehat{B}_C(t_1) + q = (\widehat{B}_C)_{\lambda q}^{MT}(t_1) \\
& \geq \text{rmin}\{(\widehat{B}_C)_{\lambda q}^{MT}(t_1 * t_2), (\widehat{B}_C)_{\lambda q}^{MT}(t_2)\} \\
& = \text{rmin}\{\lambda \cdot \widehat{B}_C(t_1 * t_2) + q, \lambda \cdot \widehat{B}_C(t_2) + q\} \\
& \lambda \cdot \widehat{B}_C(t_1) + q = \lambda \cdot \text{rmin}\{\widehat{B}_C(t_1 * t_2), \widehat{B}_C(t_2)\} + q, \\
& \lambda \cdot J_C(t_1) - s = (J_C)_{\lambda s}^{MT}(t_1) \\
& \leq \max\{(J_C)_{\lambda s}^{MT}(t_1 * t_2), (J_C)_{\lambda s}^{MT}(t_2)\} \\
& = \max\{\lambda \cdot J_C(t_1 * t_2) - s, \lambda \cdot J_C(t_2) - s\} \\
& \lambda \cdot J_C(t_1) - s = \lambda \cdot \max\{J_C(t_1 * t_2), J_C(t_2)\} - s
\end{aligned}$$

which imply $M_C(t_1) \geq \min\{M_C(t_1 * t_2), M_C(t_2)\}, \widehat{B}_C(t_1) \geq \text{rmin}\{\widehat{B}_C(t_1 * t_2), \widehat{B}_C(t_2)\}, J_C(t_1) \leq \max\{J_C(t_1 * t_2), J_C(t_2)\}$ for all $t_1, t_2 \in Y$. Hence C is a **MBJNID** of Y .

Theorem 3.5 Intersection of any two **MBJNMT** $C_{\lambda p, q, s}^{MT}$ of a **MBJNID** C of Y is a **MBJNID** of Y .

Proof. Suppose $C_{\lambda p, q, s}^{MT}$ and $C_{\lambda' p', q', s'}^{MT}$ are two **MBJNMTs** of **MBJNID** C of Y , where $p, q, s, p', q', s' \in [0, H]$ and $\lambda, \lambda' \in (0, 1]$. Assume $p \leq p', q \leq q', s \leq s'$ and $\lambda = \lambda'$. Since $C_{\lambda p, q, s}^{MT}$ and $C_{\lambda' p', q', s'}^{MT}$ are **MBJNIDs** of Y . So

$$\begin{aligned}
& ((M_C)_{\lambda p}^{MT} \cap (M_C)_{\lambda' p'}^{MT})(t_1) = \min\{(M_C)_{\lambda p}^{MT}(t_1), (M_C)_{\lambda' p'}^{MT}(t_1)\} \\
& = \min\{\lambda \cdot M_C(t_1) + p, \lambda' \cdot M_C(t_1) + p'\} \\
& = \lambda \cdot M_C(t_1) + p \\
& ((M_C)_{\lambda p}^{MT} \cap (M_C)_{\lambda' p'}^{MT})(t_1) = (M_C)_{\lambda p}^{MT}(t_1), \\
& ((\widehat{B}_C)_{\lambda q}^{MT} \cap (\widehat{B}_C)_{\lambda' q'}^{MT})(t_1) = \text{rmin}\{(\widehat{B}_C)_{\lambda q}^{MT}(t_1), (\widehat{B}_C)_{\lambda' q'}^{MT}(t_1)\} \\
& = \text{rmin}\{\lambda \cdot \widehat{B}_C(t_1) + q, \lambda' \cdot \widehat{B}_C(t_1) + q'\} \\
& = \lambda \cdot \widehat{B}_C(t_1) + q \\
& ((\widehat{B}_C)_{\lambda q}^{MT} \cap (\widehat{B}_C)_{\lambda' q'}^{MT})(t_1) = (\widehat{B}_C)_{\lambda q}^{MT}(t_1), \\
& ((J_C)_{\lambda s}^{MT} \cap (J_C)_{\lambda' s'}^{MT})(t_1) = \max\{(J_C)_{\lambda s}^{MT}(t_1), (J_C)_{\lambda' s'}^{MT}(t_1)\} \\
& = \max\{\lambda \cdot J_C(t_1) - s, \lambda' \cdot J_C(t_1) - s'\}
\end{aligned}$$

$$= \lambda \cdot J_C(t_1) - s$$

$$((J_C)_{\lambda s}^{MT} \cap (J_C)_{\lambda' s'}^{MT})(t_1) = (J_C)_{\lambda s}^{MT}(t_1).$$

Hence $C_{\lambda p, q, s}^{MT} \cap C_{\lambda' p', q', s'}^{MT}$ is **MBJNID** of Y .

Theorem 3.6 Union of any two **MBJNMT** $C_{\lambda p, q, s}^{MT}$ of a **MBJNID** C of Y is a **MBJNID** of Y .

Proof. Suppose $C_{\lambda p, q, s}^{MT}$ and $C_{\lambda' p', q', s'}^{MT}$ are two **MBJNMTs** of **MBJNID** C of Y , where $p, q, s, p', q', s' \in [0, H]$ and $\lambda, \lambda' \in (0, 1]$. Assume $p \leq p', q \leq q', s \leq s'$ and $\lambda = \lambda'$. Since $C_{\lambda p, q, s}^{MT}$ and $C_{\lambda' p', q', s'}^{MT}$ are **MBJNIDs** of Y . Then

$$((M_C)_{\lambda p}^{MT} \cup (M_C)_{\lambda' p'}^{MT})(t_1) = \max\{(M_C)_{\lambda p}^{MT}(t_1), (M_C)_{\lambda' p'}^{MT}(t_1)\}$$

$$= \max\{\lambda \cdot M_C(t_1) + p, \lambda' \cdot M_C(t_1) + p'\}$$

$$= \lambda \cdot M_C(t_1) + p$$

$$((M_C)_{\lambda p}^{MT} \cap (M_C)_{\lambda' p'}^{MT})(t_1) = (M_C)_{\lambda p}^{MT}(t_1),$$

$$((\widehat{B}_C)_{\lambda q}^{MT} \cup (\widehat{B}_C)_{\lambda' q'}^{MT})(t_1) = \text{rmax}\{(\widehat{B}_C)_{\lambda q}^{MT}(t_1), (\widehat{B}_C)_{\lambda' q'}^{MT}(t_1)\}$$

$$= \text{rmax}\{\lambda \cdot \widehat{B}_C(t_1) + q, \lambda' \cdot \widehat{B}_C(t_1) + q'\}$$

$$= \lambda \cdot \widehat{B}_C(t_1) + q$$

$$((\widehat{B}_C)_{\lambda q}^{MT} \cap (\widehat{B}_C)_{\lambda' q'}^{MT})(t_1) = (\widehat{B}_C)_{\lambda q}^{MT}(t_1),$$

$$((J_C)_{\lambda s}^{MT} \cup (J_C)_{\lambda' s'}^{MT})(t_1) = \min\{(J_C)_{\lambda s}^{MT}(t_1), (J_C)_{\lambda' s'}^{MT}(t_1)\}$$

$$= \min\{\lambda \cdot J_C(t_1) - s, \lambda' \cdot J_C(t_1) - s'\}$$

$$= \lambda \cdot J_C(t_1) - s$$

$$((J_C)_{\lambda s}^{MT} \cap (J_C)_{\lambda' s'}^{MT})(t_1) = (J_C)_{\lambda s}^{MT}(t_1)$$

4. Conclusion

In this article, we defined **MBJNMT** of **MBJ**-neutrosophic set on **G**-algebra. Moreover, deep study of **MBJNMT** will lead us to study the neutrosophic theory on some other framework. For future work, magnification can be applied on **MBJ**-neutrosophic soft set and **T**-**MBJ**-neutrosophic set.

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